

INDIRECT TRANSLATION AT THE MARGINS: STANISŁAW LEM IN ITALIAN JOURNALS AND ANTHOLOGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19332694>

Keywords: *Stanislaw Lem, Science fiction, Peripheral circulation, Relay languages, Italian reception of Polish literature*

For several decades, Italian publishers have extensively relied on indirect translation practices—a tendency that has not entirely disappeared to this day—particularly when dealing with so-called “minor languages” (*lingue minori*), including Polish. This reliance resulted not only from a shortage of qualified translators, but also from the widespread assumption that translation was a secondary, largely mechanical activity with little impact on literary reception. Such views were especially persistent in popular genres, such as science fiction, which had long been relegated to the margins of the Italian literary system and circulated primarily through periodicals, anthologies, and low-prestige formats.

The early Italian reception of Stanisław Lem (1921–2001) offers a particularly revealing case. While Lem’s “hard” science-fiction novels—perceived as philosophically serious and conceptually ambitious—were published in book form and later retranslated directly from Polish, a significant portion of his comical-satirical writing entered the Italian system through indirect, fragmentary translations disseminated in journals and collective volumes. These texts, drawn mainly from Lem’s humorous and parodic works, are notable for their extreme linguistic density, wordplay, stylistic pastiche, and intertextual irony.

Focusing on these fringe translations, my paper analyses a range of unconventional translation practices, including heavy abridgement, reinterpretation, and, in some cases, intralingual plagiarism, whereby indirect translations were recycled or reworked within the Italian literary system itself. Through a comparative reading of selected journal and anthology translations alongside later direct translations, the study identifies systematic strategies of simplification and normalization that disproportionately affect the comic-satirical dimension of Lem’s writing.

References:

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